

Consent form

Consent Form

By completing this form, you give us permission to use this case study for academic purposes and potential publications.

Thank you for helping.

Introduction

- Research Title:** Method for estimating the impact of Robotic Process Automation implementations on business processes.
- Researcher:** Bo van den Oever
- Research period:** 01/02/2020 – 31/05/2020
- Objective:** Based on this case study, I hope to validate a standardized RPA impact estimation method that supports the creation of business cases that serve expectation management in terms of costs and savings in RPA projects.
- Risks of participation:** We foresee no risks of participation. Although the participant is always, during the research period, free to withdraw from participating without giving any reason.
- Data protection:** Your personal data will only be used within the context of this research and will not be shared with any other parties that are not already involved (Ciphix & University Utrecht). Any personal data will be anonymised in further (potential) publications.
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Personal information

Full name	
Team	
Function	
Telephone	
Email	

Agreement

I have read and understand the conditions of participating in this research. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason. I declare the above to be true and agree to participate by signing this consent form.

Signature

Date
